

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RECURRING SCHEME OF STATE BANK OF INDIA AND SYSTEMATIC INVESTMENT PLAN OF SBI AMC

Mohammad Humayun Kabir Chowdhury

Independent Research Scholar, California Public University, Delaware, United States of America

Cite This Article: Mohammad Humayun Kabir Chowdhury, "A Comparative Analysis of Recurring Scheme of State Bank of India and Systematic Investment Plan of SBI AMC", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 13-17, 2024.

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Abstract:

Setting aside a fixed amount of money every month specifically for savings or investment is the best way for wealth maximization. If the question where to invest arises, then everybody probably recommend Recurring Deposits (RD) of banks. For people willing to invest a fixed amount every month rather than a single time investment of huge amount, there are many alternatives which are available and offer potentially higher returns. One such alternative is the Systematic Investment Plan (SIP) which is offered by mutual fund houses. The product works same as Recurring Deposit of bank, difference being SIP's invests in capital markets which include equity and debt instruments. SIP and RD are two popular savings plans among retail investors, which serve the purpose of long-term wealth creation. SIP is an investment plan in mutual funds, on the other hand, RD is a recurring deposit in banks. Again arises a question, which is better RD or SIP?. There lies the requirement of comparison of RD and SIP. To make prudent decision, investors should evaluate the differences between SIP and RD. So the main aim of this paper is to aware the people about the differences between the systematic investment plan and recurring deposit to achieve their long term financial goals and maximize their wealth.

Key Words: Systematic Investment Plan, Mutual Fund, Recurring Deposit, Mutual Fund Houses, Wealth Maximization.

Introduction:

Investments are the best way to maximize returns. Investment involves employment of funds with the aim of achieving additional income or growth in values. The mutual fund is the vehicle for investing in a diverse pool of assets. People focuses mostly on risk free investments such as PPF, Bank Deposits, Insurance policies, Real estate etc. But relying too much on fixed income options is just as risky as equity investments. The mutual fund option is a safer option for them. SIP is the best for those who are interested in long term regular investments.

Savings is also important as investments. It is the safest way to accumulate money. The ability to save money is the cornerstone of building wealth. It's also essential for one's sense of security. The deposit is a safe way to save money for unexpected expenses. The first and probably most important savings goal you need to consider is building up an emergency fund. You can't always predict what life has in store for you. A financial emergency may take the form of a job loss, significant medical or dental expense, unexpected home or auto repairs or something unexpected etc. There are mainly four types of deposit accounts. They are 1) Fixed Deposit, 2) Savings, 3) Recurring, 4) Current accounts. Among them Recurring Deposit is more suitable those who are interested in long term regular deposit.

Mutual Fund:

A mutual fund is tools that collect money from a number of investors who have a common Investment objective. Then they invest the money in equities, bonds, money market instruments or other securities. Each investor owns units which represent a portion of the holdings of the fund. The income generated from this investment is distributed among the investors after deducting certain expenses by calculating a schemes NAV. This fund is managed by a professional fund manager of the Asset Management Company.

Systematic Investment Plan:

A systematic investment plan is also commonly referred to as SIP. It's a plan that allows investors to make regular equal payments into mutual funds, trading accounts, or retirement accounts. Aside from these, one can also benefit from the long-term advantages of dollar-cost averaging (DCA). Dollar-cost averaging involves buying a fixed-dollar amount of a security no matter what the price might be. Keep in mind that shares can be bought at varying prices. This then means that the average cost per share of a security has the potential to decrease over time. Additionally, the risk of investing a large amount of money also decreases. Most often, liquid accounts such as money market accounts are used for funding payments. They can also be used for buying shares that go into a systematic investment plan. Additionally, most investors decide to reinvest dividends received from their holdings back into purchasing more stocks. Such actions are referred to as DRIPs or Dividend Reinvestment Plans.

Advantages of SIP:

- Management of the fund by the professionals or experts.
- Enjoy the benefits of diversification.
- The mutual fund industry is well regulated both by SEBI and AMFI.
- Market timing becomes irrelevant.
- It makes investing easier as it does not strain our monthly finances.
- Reduces the average cost.
- Result in large wealth and help fulfil dreams & aspirations of investors.

Recurring Deposit:

Recurring deposit is one of the most preferred investment schemes available in India. Risk averse investors looking for a promising investment scheme with good returns choose Recurring Deposit because it is simple and is a straightforward financial product. In a recurring deposit scheme, the investor deposits a set amount every month over a predefined tenure, which generally varies between one year to five years. The recurring deposit scheme has one major differentiating point when compared to fixed

deposits - in a fixed deposit scheme, the investor has to deposit a lump sum once and leave it untouched for a period of time. So, people who do not have a lump sum or people who are looking to invest a set amount every month usually prefer Recurring Deposits. The principal amount deposited is returned at the end of tenure along with the interest. Normally, the interest is calculated on a quarterly compounding basis for recurring deposits.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of this study is to compare recurring schemes in bank deposits and Systematic Investment Plan of mutual funds. To get more clarity here comparison is done with the recurring scheme of the State Bank of India and Systematic Investment Plan of SBI Asset Management Companies.

The main objectives are:

- To give a brief idea about SIP and RD scheme of the State Bank of India
- To know which one will give better returns SIP or RD
- To study about the role of investment in wealth maximization

The overall objective of this project is to compare SIP and RD schemes and also calculate their returns from last 10 years. So this study will definitely help the investors who are interested in long term regular investments.

Significance of the Study:

The comparison between Systematic Investment Plan and Recurring Deposit provide greater interest to several market participants as it gives valuable information about the relative performance of the SIP and RD and helps in efficient allocation of money for the investors. This study would also help the fund managers to examine their forecasting ability and revise their asset allocation decisions. It also helps the people to achieve their long term financial goals and wealth.

Scope of the Study:

The study mainly focuses on analyzing Systematic Investment Plan and Recurring Deposit schemes. It also concentrates on factors affecting the investment decision of the investors for the purpose of the present study, recurring scheme of the State Bank of India and systematic investment plan of SBI asset management companies is considered.

Limitations of the Study:

The project is limited in scope as the survey is conducted with shortage of time and also based on secondary data. So there is a lag in publication of the up to date information on various websites, journals etc. The banks were not disclosing their exact portfolio because they have a fear that it will affect the reliability of their schemes among investors.

Review of Literature:

As mentioned by Dr. Arvind Kumar Singh and Karan Veer Singh in their paper "Study of investor perception towards unconventional tool of investment with special reference to mutual funds in Phagwara Region" concluded that the most vital problem spotted is of ignorance. Investors should be made aware of the benefits. Nobody will invest until and unless he is fully convinced. Investors should be made to realize that ignorance is no longer bliss and what they are losing by not investing. 1. Mutual funds offer a lot of benefit which no other single option could offer. But most of the people are not even aware of what actually a mutual fund is. Young investors as well as persons at the height of their career would like to go for advisors due to lack of expertise and time. 2. Younger people aged fewer than 35 will be a key new customer group into the future, so making greater efforts with younger customers who show some interest in investing should pay off. 3. Customers with graduate level education are easier to sell and there is a large untapped market there. To succeed, however, advisors must provide sound advice and high quality.

Mathumitha (2015) revealed in the study that in order to meet the future plans of the children many people invest in recurring deposit. The study also suggested that adopting an advertisement strategy will increase the number of deposits.

D. Koreshashikant and Dr. R.B. Teli (2015) in their study identified that towards post office schemes people who have clear perception are medium and small investors. The study also recommends that, in order to create awareness about the financial schemes in post offices an essential strategic planning is necessary to fight against private institutions.

Discussed by Dr. Aruna K and M. Senthamil Selvi in their paper "the scenario of mutual fund investment in systematic investment plan (sip) in Vellore district"(2017) analyzed Private employees prefer to invest than others. Male respondents are more preferable to invest in a systematic investment plan in a mutual fund than female respondents. With regard to education most of the respondents of graduate persons have intension on saving habits. 54.7% of the respondents were between the annual incomes of 100000 – 300000. 92.7% of respondents were aware of Systematic Investment Plan. The analysis revealed that 47.3% of the respondents were preferred to save on the tax savings scheme of a mutual fund. 34.7% of respondents invest a sum of 5000 – 10000 every month. 34.7% of respondents consider safety as top most important factor. From the regression analysis it is revealed that there is a relationship between age and opinion regarding investment. The investments should be in such a way that it should match the Inflation.

As mentioned by Dr.T.Unnamalai in his paper "A study on awareness of investors about the mutual fund investments in musiri taluk"(2016). He noted that nowadays investors prefer to diversify their risks and the returns should be higher, tax exemptions, etc. Today many institutions are busy in providing wealth management services to its investors. But these services are very costly. Due to this reason the mutual fund industries gaining importance and attracts more investors. The present study analyses the mutual fund investments in relation to investors'awareness. In this study above the awareness about the schemes, the study is trying to find out the various investments other than mutual funds. Nearly 75% of the investors are having investments other than mutual funds. The study also find out the opinion of the Investors and perception has been studied relating to various issues like type of mutual fund scheme, main objective behind investing in mutual fund scheme, level of satisfaction, role of financial advisors and brokers, investors' opinion relating to factors that attract them to invest in mutual funds, sources of information, deficiencies in the services provided by the mutual fund managers, challenges before the Indian mutual fund industry etc. The study reveals that there is a positive growth in their investments and majority of them expects safety, diversification of

their risks, high returns etc. Majority of them expects better advice from the agents. Instead of the agents regular awareness campaign should be conducted by the companies. It will win the confidence of the investors.

Confidence level of investors was analysed by Priti Mane in his paper titled “A Study of Investors Perception towards Mutual Funds in the City of Aurangabad”(2016) in which she took thirty investors of Aurangabad city. Her objective was to study the investors view towards mutual fund as per the sample size and test which is applied to the study. She found that the investors are not choosing or feeling confident in investing in mutual fund because they think that mutual fund is risky than other investment option. The awareness level of mutual fund among the investors are very low because of only having the partial knowledge about the mutual fund which prevent them to invest in mutual fund to avoid risk bearing factor and fear of losing money .The most preference of the investors are the fixed deposit because they feel it is the safest and returns are fixed and not having fear of losing the money. Apart from these found that there are investors facing various problems in selecting mutual fund as an investment option because of share market uncertainties and risk associated with it so investors avoid the investing in mutual fund

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a science of studying how research is done scientifically.The study is conducted in the following manner:

Collection of Data:

This is a descriptive study conducted by using secondary data. The secondary data is collected from the websites of SBI and SBI AMC.

Method of Analysis:

The general information about SIP and RD collect from the website of SBI and Various websites of AMCs.

Tools of Analysis:

The tools applied for data analysis is Compound Interest and Paired Samples Test. The study used necessary graphs and diagrams wherever necessary.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table Showing SIP Returns

Year	Expected Rate of Return	Investment Amount	Maturity Value
1	12%	Rs.12000	Rs.12809.33
2	12%	Rs.24000	Rs.27243.20
3	12%	Rs.36000	Rs.43507.65
4	12%	Rs.48000	Rs.61834.83
5	12%	Rs.60000	Rs.82486.37
6	12%	Rs.72000	Rs.105757.03
7	12%	Rs.84000	Rs.131979
8	12%	Rs.96000	Rs.161526.57
9	12%	Rs.108000	Rs.194821.51
10	12%	Rs.120000	Rs.232339.08

Table showing Recurring Deposit Returns

Year	Investment	Interest Rate for General Public	Maturity Value for General Public	Interest Rate for Senior Citizen	Maturity Value for Senior Citizen
1	Rs.12000	6.40	Rs.12442	6.90	Rs.12457
2	Rs.24000	6.40	Rs.25658	6.90	Rs.25795
3	Rs.36000	6.25	Rs.39668	6.75	Rs.39980
4	Rs.48000	6.25	Rs.54618	6.75	Rs.55193
5	Rs.60000	6.25	Rs.70527	6.75	Rs.71459
6	Rs.72000	6.25	Rs.87451	6.75	Rs.88850
7	Rs.84000	6.25	Rs.105458	6.75	Rs.107446
8	Rs.96000	6.25	Rs.124617	6.75	Rs.127331
9	Rs.108000	6.25	Rs.145001	6.75	Rs.148590
10	Rs.120000	6.25	Rs.166690	6.75	Rs.171322

Inferences:

- For 1 year, SIP was making a return of 12809.33, but RD was only generating a return of 12442 in case of general public and 12457 in case of senior citizen.
- For 2 years, SIP made a return of 27243.20, but RD was only generating a return of 25658 in case of general public and 25795 in case of senior citizen.
- For 3 years, SIP made a return of 43507.65, but RD was only generating a return of 39668 in case of general public and 39980 in case of senior citizen.
- For 4 years, SIP made a return of 61834.83, but RD was only generating a return of 55618 in case of general public and 55193 in case of senior citizen.
- For 5 years, SIP made a return of 82486.37, but RD was only generating a return of 70527 in case of general public and 71459 in case of senior citizen.
- For 6 years, SIP made a return of 105757.03, but RD was only generating a return of 87451 in case of general public and 88850 in case of senior citizen.

- For 7 years, SIP was making a return of 131979, but RD was only generating a return of 105458 in case of general public and 107446 in case of senior citizen.
- For 8 years, SIP made a return of 161526.57, but RD was only generating a return of 124617 in case of general public and 127331 in case of senior citizen.
- For 9 years, SIP made a return of 194821.51, but RD was only generating a return of 145001 in case of general public and 148590 in case of senior citizen.
- For 10 years, SIP made a maturity value of 232339.08, but RD was only generating a maturity value of 166690 in case of general public and 171322 in case of senior citizen.

Paired Samples Test:

Comparison between Investment and Return towards General Public and Senior Citizens:

		Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Df	Sig
Pair 1	Investment - Interest Rate	6.59	36331.84	5.74	9	.000
Pair 2	Investment - Maturity value for general public	-1.721	15899.97	-3.42	9	.008
Pair 3	Investment - Interest rate for senior citizen	6.599	36331.84	5.74	9	.000
Pair 4	Investment - Maturity value for senior citizen	-1.884	17476.21	-3.40	9	.008

The above table depicts that there is a relationship between investment made by the respondents and the maturity value among general public and senior citizens as the level of significance is less than 0.05.

Comparison between Investment Amount and Maturity Value with reference to SIP Returns:

		Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	t	Df	Sig
Pair 1	Investment Amount - Maturity Value	-3.94	38166.68	12069.36	-3.267	9	.010

Interpretation:

It depicts that the investment amount with SIP have an impact towards maturity value with reference to SIP returns.

Findings:

- From the analysis, it can be clearly understood that SIP is better as compared to RD in terms of returns.
- The study found that the return of SIP is not assured, but it is good if investment is done for long periods. Return for RD is fixed and it is less risky and safest form of savings.
- The RD is opted by the investor only when investors wish to reduce the risk. As the risk is reduced the return also will be low.
- There is a relationship between the investment made by the respondents and the maturity value among general public and senior citizens.
- Investment amount with SIP have an impact towards maturity value with reference to SIP returns.

Suggestions:

- Investors should invest in mutual funds and recurring deposits to allow money to grow. They can invest in these tools to get good returns, based on their risk appetite. Once the investment plan decided, make sure to read the fine print thoroughly to understand the product.
- The companies should dispatch their annual report in time to their investors so that the investors are informed about the company's financial position. This will help the investor to know the status of their investment.
- Strict regulations should be enforced by SEBI with regard to Corporate Governance. SEBI should enforce strict regulations on mutual fund companies where frauds are committed. There has been a conflict of personal interest of fund managers in the past. SEBI should enforce, strict regulations, so that other mutual fund companies will be deterred from committing frauds in future.
- Investors should make investments by considering their risk appetite in order to allow their investments to grow and generate better returns. It is recommended, to consult & keep in touch with a qualified adviser or firm before taking a decision about investments.

Conclusion:

Systematic Investment Plans are market linked. Its returns are not guaranteed. Recurring Deposits are one of the safest investment options. So the returns are guaranteed at a fixed interest rate. SIP gives us good returns on long term investment options. In case of RD the investment is in bank deposits and the investors getting interesting. It could change over time. Likewise the return on SIP depends on market and can vary across schemes and market conditions. The major disadvantage of a Recurring Deposit is that it is not tax efficient. TDS (Tax Deducted at Source) is applicable on the interest income from RD.

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